

IN-PLANE SHEAR PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY USING V-NOTCHED SPECIMEN AND DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

In-plane shear properties of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP) were investigated by the digital image correlation (DIC) analysis under the V-Notched Rail Shear Method (ASTM D7078). Three kinds of materials, unidirectional CFRTP (UD by Mitsubishi Rayon), carbon mat reinforced thermoplastic composites (CMT by Toray) and chopped-tapes reinforced thermoplastic composites (CTT by Toyobo) were used for this study. UD and CMT specimens showed uniform shear strain distributions in the central section between two notches. In case of UD specimen, the failure progress is observed along the carbon fiber direction initiated from notched tips in the specimen where the slightly larger shear strain was observed. In case of CMT specimen, the principle strain distribution was observed spread at an angle of 45° with respect to the tensile load axis. The failure progress direction is strongly correlated with the principal strain distribution. In case of CTT specimen, the localization of shear strain distribution in the notched central section was analyzed and observed by DIC method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, CFRTP is expected to be used for next-generation light-weight vehicles because of its high specific stiffness and strength, good workability and high formability. When it comes to using thermoplastic resin which performs comparatively elasto-plastic behavior, mechanical properties of CFRTP shows nonlinear complex behavior in shear direction. Instead of that, it is difficult to evaluate and detect in-plane shear properties of fiber reinforced composites with high accuracy because of multi-axial stress-mode by any standard shear test method. In order to apply computer aided engineering (CAE) to accelerated and high-quality development for mass-produced automobile, it is highly demanded to evaluate and validate in-plane shear properties of CFRTP by the pure shear test method.

In-plane shear properties of the composite materials are estimated by various testing method. Some examples follow. ASTM D 5379 (Iosipescu method) is asymmetrically loaded through four edges of test specimen which has a small gauge section whose length is about 11 mm. ISO14129 is given by the plus or minus 45 degrees tension test method only adapted to composite laminate with unidirectional fiber or composite fabrics oriented +/- 45 degrees from the specimen axis. However, it is not easy to adopt these testing methods by using strain gauge for the CFRTP specimen with discontinuous fibers because the past researches show that it tends to cause some strain concentration in gauge section.^{[1] [2] [3]}

Digital image correlation (DIC) analysis is a technique which is capable of comparing the random patterns on the surface of the test specimen after deformation with those before deformation to

quantify the elongation magnitude of defined measuring area. It is a good match with computer aided engineering (CAE), which is an analytical technique used for computerized product design simulation, because both techniques of DIC and CAE are highly prospective to be correlated with each other. In the past, for a long time, the DIC analysis were used as an estimation technique of material properties, and various techniques are used by the digital image which obtained by CCD camera, STM, X-ray CT 3D systems were developed now. ^[4]

In this study, in-plane shear properties of CFRTP were investigated by digital DIC analysis under the V-Notched Rail Shear Method (ASTM D7078), which makes it possible to use a large gauge section whose length is about 31 mm.

2 SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The materials used in the experiment were three kinds of composites, 0° unidirectional CFRTP (UD, by Mitsubishi Rayon), mat type of CFRTP (CMT, by Toray) and chopped-tapes CFRTP (CTT, Toyobo). All of them consist of carbon fiber and polypropylene. Above all, CMT is composed of randomly-oriented discontinuous-fiber mat with in-plane isotropic, and CTT is composed of randomly-oriented chopped-tapes laminate with in-plane quasi-isotropic. The information of test samples is shown in Table 1. The dimension of test specimen determined by ASTM D 7078 is indicated in Fig.1. The orthogonal strain gauges (KFG-2-120-D16, by Kyowa) were bonded to the center between the notch tips in the gauge section of the specimen.

In-plane shear testing was conducted at room temperature. The test apparatus is shown in Fig.2. The shear stress-strain curves and synchronous test video movies were obtained by utilizing precision universal testing machine (Auto-graph AG-100kNX, by Shimadzu), non-contacted video extensometer (TRViewX120S, by Shimadzu), V-notched rail shear test fixture (Model No. WTF-NR, by Wyoming test fixtures) and dynamic strain measurement system (DC-97, by Tokyo sokki kenkyujyo). Principle strain distribution, shear strain distribution and measurement value at several points by virtual extensometer were obtained by the 2D-DIC analysis software (DAVIS8, by LAVISION). 31×31 pixel subset and 15 pixel step sizes were used as some parameters for the 2D-DIC analysis.

Strain gauges and virtual strain gauges in the 2D-DIC analysis software were mounted on the central of the gauge section of test specimens oriented at angles of $+45^\circ$ and -45° with respect to loading axis. Additionally, two more virtual strain gauges in the 2D-DIC analysis software were positioned at upper and lower area in central gauge section for evaluating the presence of position dependence of measuring area.

Sample	Matrix	CF	Vf (%)
UD	Polypropylene	TR50	45
CMT	Polypropylene	T700	20
CTT	Polypropylene	TR50	50

Table 1: Sample information.

Fig.1 Test specimen

Fig.2 Shear testing system

3 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SHEAR STRESS-STRAIN CURVE AND SHEAR STRAIN DISTRIBUTION

3.1. Shear testing of UD specimen

Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve are shown in Fig.3. Initially, a small crack was observed around the upper notched tip when shear stress of UD specimen indicates 27 MPa with a small peak in shear stress-stroke curve. The crack propagated along the fiber direction without a decrease in shear stress. Finally, another crack was also observed around the notched lower tip and the specimen was broken incompletely without a significant decrease in shear stress.

Shear stress-strain curves of UD specimen measured by strain gauges and the 2D-DIC analysis are shown in Fig.4(a). Fig.4 (b) also shows the distributions of maximum principle strain and maximum shear strain in the gauge section. Shear stress-strain curves measured by the 2D-DIC analysis in the central section were well accorded with that measured by strain gauge. UD specimen showed uniform shear strain distribution in the notched central section. However, the strain values measured near at upper and lower points in the gauge section were slightly larger than the value of strain gauges. From the test results, it is clear that maximum shear strain distribution is highly relevant with the strain concentration around notched tips.

Fig.3 Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve of 0° UD specimen

(a) Shear stress-strain curves measured by strain gauges and the 2D-DIC analysis

(b) Maximum normal and shear strain distribution at about 30 MPa

Fig.4 Results of shear test (0° UD specimen)

3.2 Shear testing of CMT specimen

Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve are shown in Fig.5. Shear stress-strain curves of CMT specimen measured by strain gauges and the 2D-DIC analysis are shown in Fig.6 (a). Fig.6 (b) also shows the distributions of maximum principle strain and maximum shear strain in the notched central section. The failure cracks propagated at an angle of 45 degrees with respect to the axis of loading direction. Every shear stress-strain curve evaluated at each point by the 2D-DIC analysis was well accorded with that measured by strain gauges. Maximum shear strain distribution was highly uniform in the gauge section including the notched area which are strain-concentrated. The failure progressing direction is strongly correlated with the highest section of normal strain distribution. It means that the failure mechanism of CMT is influenced dominantly by tensile fracture mode related to maximum strain.

Fig.5 Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve of CMT specimen

(a) Stress-shear strain curves measured by strain gauges and the 2D-DIC analysis

(b) Maximum normal and shear strain distribution at about 120 MPa

Fig.6 Results of shear test (CMT specimen)

3.3. Shear testing of CTT specimen

Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve are shown in Fig.7. Shear stress-strain curves of CTT specimen measured by strain gauges and the 2D-DIC analysis are shown in Fig.8 (a). Fig.8 (b) also shows the distribution of maximum principle strain and maximum shear strain in the notched central section. The initial cracks which originated from upper and lower notched sections propagated at an angle of 45 degrees with respect to the axis of loading direction. The partial fracture was initialized from the lower notched section and the failure area was spreading and progressing toward central area. The highest concentration of maximum normal and shear strain were observed in the upper notched section. This analysis suggests that it is difficult to evaluate strain dispersion by using real strain gauge with short gauge length in the notched central section because the size and orientation of chopped tapes where the strain gauges are mounted on influences the actual strain measured value. Shear stress-strain curves measured by the 2D-DIC analysis targeting around the central and lower

section were well accorded with the result of strain gauge measurement. In contrast, the strain values in the upper section measured by the 2D-DIC analysis was larger than the actual measured value by strain gauges. The shear failure mechanism indicated complex behavior and the 2D-DIC analysis could detect a localized shear strain concentration in the gauge section.

Fig.7 Fracture appearance and shear stress-stroke curve of CTT specimen

Fig.8 Results of shear test (CTT specimen)

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated about applicability and validity of V-notched shear test method with strain distribution analysis by DIC technique for evaluating in-plane shear properties of various types of CFRTF.

The shear deformation test and DIC analysis on UD specimens showed the uniform shear strain distribution in the notched central section and the shear strain concentration was slightly observed in upper and lower notched sections. Shear stress-strain curve of UD specimen in the notched central section measured by the 2D-DIC analysis was similar to the actual measured value by strain gauges. The shear deformation test and DIC analysis on CMT specimen showed the uniform shear strain

distribution in the gauge section. The multipoint measurement and strain distribution view by using the 2D-DIC analysis have effectiveness as a method for estimating entire strain dispersion because the localized shear strain concentration could be detected in case of non-uniform material like CTT specimen. It is effective to carry out both local-section measurements by strain gauges and broad-area evaluation by the 2D-DIC analysis simultaneously because it helps to investigate the failure mechanism of various types of CFRTP, continuous-fiber reinforced type, mat-reinforced type and chopped-tapes reinforced type.

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